

INTRODUCING THE USE OF NEW APPROACHES AND METHODS IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the use of new methods and techniques in teaching chemistry. With these methods and techniques, students will better understand and learn the subject. In the process of studying chemistry topics, tools that support such methods as “5x5x5”, “Decision Tree”, “Experiential Learning Cycle” and “Black Box” are presented. Information is provided on the definition, application, and effectiveness of these methods. It has been determined based on tests that when the above-selected methods are used during training, they lead to increased efficiency.*

Keywords: *concept, method, methodology, lesson, practical exercise, teaching, didactics, small group, upbringing, “5x5x5”, “Decision tree”, “Experiential learning cycle” and “Black box”.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the higher education system is receiving increased attention. Therefore, chemistry teachers must be able to impart the secrets of science to students in a quality manner, using our skills and talents.

Colloid chemistry is a complex, but at the same time very interesting science. When explaining the topics, it is advisable to choose teaching methods that are appropriate for them, based on the content of the topic being covered and the age psychology of the students. For example, the “Chemist's Ball” method can be used to review topics in general or to focus students' attention on the subject.

Nowadays, the higher education system is receiving more and more attention. Therefore, teachers must be able to convey the secrets of chemistry to students using our pedagogical skills and scientific talent.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The use of practical exercises and interactive methods is of great importance in teaching chemistry and reinforcing theoretical knowledge.

The purpose of the article is to select convenient, understandable interactive methods for students and teachers to master chemistry. Interactive methods for students present the main part of the work in the form of questions and tasks, interesting experiments, pictures, graphs and tables, while teachers have full control over their students' work and organize wider work with programs. As a result, the teacher works individually with each student during the lesson process to reinforce theoretical knowledge, making the lesson more productive and high-quality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In turn, the state can obtain highly educated and competitive specialists only by creating favorable conditions for their training and development within educational institutions that use the most advanced methods and methods of teaching fundamental sciences and higher professional disciplines.

Below we will briefly describe some of the methods that have been and can be used in the teaching process.

"5x5x5" METHOD

Using the "5x5x5" method, it is possible to simultaneously involve all students in a specific activity, solve a specific task or problem, as well as determine the capabilities of each member of the groups and learn their views. In this method, 5 groups of 5 participants each discuss a problem posed by the teacher. After the allotted time, the teacher re-forms the 5 groups. Each of the re-formed groups contains one representative from the previous 5 groups. The members of the newly formed group present to their teammates the conclusion presented by their group as a solution to the problem and discuss these solutions together.

The advantages of the "5x5x5" method are as follows:

- encourages each member of the group to be active;
- ensures the expression of personal views by them;
- develops the skills of listening to the opinions of other members of the group;
- teaches the ability to summarize several ideas put forward, as well as to defend one's own opinion.

Most importantly, each of the training participants acts as both a discussion participant, a listener, and a speaker for a short period of time (20 minutes).

This method can also be used in several groups consisting of a small number of students. However, when using the "5x5x5" method among large groups, it is necessary to increase the time. Because in such classes, a little more time is required for both discussion and information provision. When using the method in question, there is an opportunity for groups to work on one or more topics in the classes.

Using the "5x5x5" method in the educational process requires the teacher to be proactive, have pedagogical skills, and be able to form groups appropriately. Incorrect group formation can lead to incorrect completion of tasks.

Using this method, training is organized in the following order:

Before the lesson begins, the teacher places 5 chairs around 5 tables.

The teacher divides the students into 5 groups. When dividing the students into groups, each seat is named and those who receive the named sheets take their seats.

After the students have settled in, the teacher announces the topic of the lesson and gives specific tasks to the groups. A certain time is set and a discussion process is organized.

The teacher monitors the activities of the groups, provides advice and guidance to group members where necessary, and asks the groups to complete their discussions after making sure that the tasks assigned by the groups have been correctly solved.

After the time allotted for discussion is up, the teacher re-forms the groups. Each of the re-formed groups will have one representative from each of the previous 5 groups. The members of the newly formed groups will present to their peers the conclusion presented by their group as a solution to the problem and discuss these solutions together.

"DECISION TREE " METHOD

The "decision tree" method is a technical approach aimed at mastering somewhat complex topics in the foundations of a particular science, reaching specific conclusions on the basis of a comprehensive and thorough analysis of certain issues, and finding the most acceptable and correct one among several conclusions presented on a given problem.

This method also serves to re-analyze and fully understand the essence of decisions (or conclusions) made in previous situations.

The “Decision Tree” allows you to determine the level of knowledge of several dozen students, summarize and evaluate their opinions. The use of this method in the educational process creates the opportunity to analyze in detail each option presented by students, their acceptable and unacceptable aspects when making a rational decision (coming to a conclusion) on a specific problem.

The "decision tree" method is used under the following conditions:

Before the start of the lesson, the teacher identifies a topic-related problem for discussion and analysis. Prepares posters to record the conclusions reached by the groups.

The teacher divides the students into groups of 4 or 6. A certain amount of time is set for solving the problem and making the most appropriate decision.

During the decision-making process, the levels of acceptability and unacceptability of the options presented by each member of the group are discussed in detail. The advantages and disadvantages of each option are recorded. Based on the options presented, the group members come to a consensus on a method that will serve to positively solve the problem.

When the time allotted for discussion is up, each group member reports their group's decision. If necessary, under the guidance of the teacher, all students compare the conclusions (or decisions) with each other.

If questions arise regarding the conclusions (or decisions) made on the problem, the answers are returned, and any ambiguities are clarified. If all groups reach the same decision on the problem, the teacher explains the reason for this.

The unique feature of the “Decision Tree” method is that it is directly applied to a specific project. This project looks like this:

"Decision Tree" Method					
Common problem					
Solution 1		Solution 2		Decision option 3	
Advantage	Disadvantage	Advantage	Disadvantage	Advantage	Disadvantage
Decision:					

THE METHOD OF "EXPERIENCE-BASED LEARNING CYCLE"

This method is based on the following 4 main factors:

- reflective observation;
- abstract inference;
- preparation for active experimentation;
- conducting a concrete experiment.

Each of the factors listed above is based on a specific idea:

Create an environment that allows students to critically examine and reflect on the content of the exercises (reflective observation);

Provide students with the necessary theoretical knowledge;

Create conditions for summarizing and drawing conclusions from the opinions expressed on the problem (abstract conclusion);

Provide students with the opportunity to develop exercises that are well-formed and at the same time need to be checked again (preparation for active experimentation);

Draw the final conclusion from personal experience and use it in your work (conduct a concrete experiment).

"BLACK BOX" METHOD

The goal of using this method in the educational process is to achieve thorough mastery of the subject by students, as well as to encourage them to be active, work collaboratively, manage certain situations, and develop logical thinking skills.

When using the method, the following actions are organized:

- students are paired;
- pairs are tasked with recording key concepts (key words, dates, symbols, numbers, etc.) that illustrate the essence of the topic on cards;
- the teacher, in collaboration with the students, checks the completion of the task by the groups;
- one member of the group who completed the task correctly acts as the teacher and writes the solution to the task on the board;
- students in the group interpret the idea recorded on the board (say what key words, dates, symbols, numbers, etc. mean);
- the student who answered correctly acts as a teacher, instructing the pairs to create a diagram, table, or image that illustrates the essence of the topic, and with the help of the teacher, checks the completion of the task.

CONCLUSION

I widely use the methods and techniques described above in colloid chemistry lessons. All methods serve to increase students' interest in science, which improves the quality of education. I recommend that you use these methods and techniques, too.

The methods described above increase the productivity of the educational process, develop students' independent thinking, increase their enthusiasm and interest in knowledge, and form the skills and competencies to consolidate, assimilate knowledge, and freely use it in practice.

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